

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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Abstract

In the present deliverable D5.16, following the original plan deployed in D5.9 (Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan), and the reports D5.10 (no1 - M12) and D5.11 (no2 - M24) on “Dissemination and Communication Activities”, we report for the first time separately the “Outreach and Liaison Activities” with a similar report due to the end of the project on month 48. We define clearly outreach and liaison activities as those activities that do not disseminate directly academic and scientific findings of the project (as these are presented separately in D5.10/D5.11/ and later one in D5.12/D5.13 - month 36th and 48th respectively) rather than mainly raise awareness of the implications and the impact of our project through wide-range events appealing to broader audiences, as well as direct liaisons with other projects of similar quests, including the ones from the same Call (i-Seed, SmartLagoon, ReSET, WatchPlant) that we share common deliverables in the Environmental Intelligence front (D5.19 in M12/D5.20 on M24; D5.21/5.22 on M36 and on M48 respectively). The present document D5.16 covers the first 24 months of the project.

1. Outreach

We start this report by listing outreach activities during the first 24 months of the RAMONES projects, in chronological order:

- The RAMONES Technical Manager, Dr. Angelos Mallios, gave an invited presentation to the Black Sea CONNECT Innovation Workshop. The event took place on Feb 2nd, 2022.

Figure 1 - Dr. Angelos Mallios is presenting at the Black Sea CONNECT Innovation Workshop

- The RAMONES project team contributed to Open Science by its Data Management Plan using ARGOS technology presented by the RAMONES WP6 leader, Ms Eleni Petra (NKUA/RAMONES) on March 3rd, 2022 at People's University of the Greek Society of Friends of the People.

Figure 2 - Photos of Ms Petra's presentation during the event at People's University

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- Associate Professor Evi Nomikou (NKUA/RAMONES) was mentioned in #BreakTheBias in Science and Technology open conversation organized by Athena research and innovation center on 9th of March 2022 and its newly founded Unit of Women in Innovation, led by our RAMONES WP6 leader E. Petra (<https://www.athenarc.gr/en/events/breakthebias>). This topic is of utmost importance as it promotes gender equality in research and innovation. The event attracted a broad audience.

Figure 3 - Assoc. Prof. Evi Nomikou during the #BreakTheBias in Science and Technology event

- A RAMONES webinar took place on the 28th of June 2022 on 'Hunting radioactivity in the Depths of the Ocean' that was led by the RAMONES PI, Associate Professor Theo J. Mertzimekis aiming at a very broad audience and communicating in lay terms the aims and objectives of this specific and similar project to RAMONES.

Figure 4 - The lead screen of the webinar by Assoc. Prof. T.J.Mertzimekis

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- Professor Kostas Nikolopoulos (UDUR/RAMONES) presented at the Arab Open University in Kuwait the objectives and progress of the RAMONES project and highlighted the impact of the RAMONES project. The event was organized on the 29th of June 2022 attracting an audience of 38 participants.
- The RAMONES team also presented the work of the RAMONES project at the Gulf University of Science and Technology in Kuwait on the 30th of June 2022 with 7 participants attending.
- The RAMONES team was active during the 86th International Fair of Thessaloniki which took place between 10-18 September 2022. The Fair is the major international expo event in Greece attracting thousands of visitors annually. More details on this event will be presented in Section 3.3.2

Figure 5 - WP6 Leader, Ms Eleni Petra, showcasing the RAMONES project during the 86th Int'l Fair of Thessaloniki

- Another event the RAMONES project members participated actively was the Researcher's Night organized at the premises of the National Technical University of Athens (30 Sep 2022; <https://researchersnight.gr/2022-αθήνα>). More details on this event are presented in Section 2.2.

Figure 6 - Researcher's Night at the National Technical University of Athens (30.09.2022)

- The RAMONES team presented in the Quarterly meet-up of the UK chapter of the International Institute of Forecasters on the 11th of November 2022. The meeting had over 20 participants both online and in-person. The presentation by the RAMONES team highlighted the importance of having mechanisms in place to produce risk assessments and forecast future behavior for the benefit of stakeholders.
- A workshop took place on the 21st of November 2022 at Durham university focusing on the latest developments of environmental intelligence, with 3 presentations by experts in their respective fields. The event was coordinated by Professor Konstantinos Nikolopoulos, with the RAMONES PI being present, attracting 20 participants including scientists and a general audience. The event took place in the Senior Common Room of the University college (the Castle) at Durham, and as such the audience was diverse and quite interested in the event and the implications of the findings of the project. Fruitful discussions took place during and after the event in which the audience showed particular interest in the progress, as well as the direct and indirect outcomes of the RAMONES project.

Figure 7 - Showcasing the RAMONES project during the Durham workshop (21.11.2022)

Figure 8 - Professor Kostas Nikolopoulos speaking to the audience during the Durham workshop

Outreach events listed below have already been reported in an earlier Deliverable (D5.10, M12). Nevertheless, as the present document is the first one reporting separately on Outreach

and Liaison Activities, the outreach events are listed briefly for completeness of the reporting on the relevant actions undertaken by the RAMONES consortium during the first 24 months of the project. For full details, please see D5.10.

- The RAMONES/IST-ID team participated in the 2021 Blue School Lisbon Regional Meeting, hosted by the Blue School Program/Ministry of Science of Portugal on the 26th of February 2021 with 150 participants attending.
- The RAMONES/UDUR team presented in the Institute for Hazard Risk and Resilience weekly seminar discussing the nature, progress and objectives of the project with 13 in-person participants.
- RAMONES co-organized the Blue Research & Innovation Days (19-23 May 2021) with an audience of 63 participants.
- The RAMONES/UCA was present at La celebration de 50 ans de l' IN2P3 au LPC de Clermont Ferrand with over 100 participants attending the event on the 18th of June 2021.
- The RAMONES/IST-ID team participated in the Meeting with Science and Technology, organized by the Ministry of Science and Technology in Lisbon, Portugal took place between 28-30 June 2021 with over 2000 participants attending the event.
- Showcasing RAMONES at the 85th Thessaloniki International Fair, (11 and 19 September 2021).
- RAMONES reached out at World Oceans Day at the University of Genova, Italy, 14 September 2021. The focus was on Marine Robotics with over 50 participants attending.
- Showcasing RAMONES at the Southampton Fair hosted by Oceans Business between the 12 and 14th of October 2021 with around 1000 participants attending the fair.
- RAMONES/IST-ID was present at FIC.A 2021, International Science Festival (12-17 October 2021), an event attracting around 40'000 participants.
- The Open Day at the IST-TagusPark Campus on the 6th of November 2021 was another event that members of the RAMONES team participated in, an event that attracted over 1000 participants.

2. Events and activities

RAMONES has been active in various events and joint venture activities targeting citizen awareness and dissemination of the project. Most of the activities have been carried out mainly through digital channels due to the global COVID-19 pandemic in 2022.

All of them have been reported on the RAMONES website (considering the goals, the challenges, the work carried out and the results) and disseminated through the RAMONES digital channels.

2.1 Conferences & workshops RAMONES (co)-organized or participated in

The most relevant workshops and conferences (co)-organized or participated by the RAMONES team, reported and disseminated through all RAMONES digital channels during this period:

Table 1 - Workshops and conferences (co)organised or participated by RAMONES

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
UN Oceans 2022 Conference UN Oceans	Conference	participation	27/6-1/7/2022
Quarterly Forecasting Forum (UK Chapter): Durham 2022	Seminar	participation	11/11/2022
Latest developments of Environmental intelligence: Measuring and Communicating risks from Radioactivity in the Oceans	Workshop	participation	21/11/2022

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Figure 9 - Examples of workshops and conferences

Figure 10 - Examples of workshops and conferences

2.2 Fairs and exhibitions participated

RAMONES as has been mentioned above actively participated in two events the second year of the project: 1. the International Fair of Thessaloniki 2022 and 2. The Researchers Night Event.

RAMONES representatives attended the commercial [International Fair of Thessaloniki 2022](#) that is held every year in Greece. During the duration of the Fair, RAMONES established links with more than 30 projects and 25 Research Centers' representatives participating in the International Fair, governmental representatives, regional and municipalities' stakeholders and policy makers, as well as with visitors to the multi-day event. Some synergies with other projects, research initiatives and industrial partners, as well as with relevant ministries and policy makers have been identified and a collaboration may be realized in the near future.

Figure 11 - RAMONES participation during the International Fair of Thessaloniki (Sep 2022)

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RAMONES partners also presented an overview of the project and its objectives to the general public in the Researchers Night Open Event in Greece held in the premises of the National Technical University of Athens mentioned also above. In the specific yearly event, scientists from various scientific fields discuss with children and young scientists about different scientific topics and multiple technological innovations promoting citizen awareness.

3. Liaison

Hereafter we list the project switch which formal liaisons has been established and maintained throughout the RAMONES project:

3.1 Liaison with H2020 projects from the same FET call

- Liaised with the i-Seed project
- Liaised with the SmartLagoon project
- Liaised with the ReSET project
- Liaised with the WatchPlant project

With the above four projects, RAMONES has co-organized and participated in joint sessions during the two GoodIT conferences in 2021 and 2022, while common deliverables in the Environmental Intelligence front (5.19/5.20 in month 24/5.22/5.23) have been prepared and submitted jointly. The 5 projects collaborate throughout their timelines in shaping the new grounds of Environmental Intelligence in Europe, identifying synergies, strengthening their research potential, but also highlighting important steps required for open dissemination of their results to a broader scale. The joint deliverables contain several details, which are not included in the present manuscript to avoid repetition.

3.2 Liaison with H2020 projects

- Liaised with the **H2020 NEANIAS** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021
The EU H2020 project NEANIAS (Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges) is a project that comprehensively addresses the challenges set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. NEANIAS (<https://www.neanias.eu>) promotes Open Science practices and plays an active role in the materialization of the EOSC ecosystem by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities; actively contributing to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of EOSC. NEANIAS deals with the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

RAMONES and NEANIAS have co-signed an MoU to explore synergies and collaboration, especially in the domain of underwater research.

- Liaised with the **H2020 EuroSea** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021

The H2020 project EuroSea (<https://eurosea.eu/>) works to improve the European ocean observing and forecasting system in a global context. EuroSea brings together key European actors of ocean observing and forecasting with users of oceanographic products and services. The EuroSea innovation demonstrators are focused on operational services, ocean health, and climate.

RAMONES have liaised with EuroSea during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project, agreeing to strengthen their collaboration in the future.

- Liaised with the **H2020 Infore** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021
RAMONES have liaised with the EU H2020 Infore project (<https://www.infore-project.eu/>) during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project. The projects discussed the preparation of a MoU in February 2021, but due to the upcoming end of Infore timeline (March 2021), that was not possible.

- Liaised with the **H2020 MASTER** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021
The overarching objective of MASTER (<http://www.master-project-h2020.eu/>) is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of organisations working on a joint research programme to define new methods to build, manage and analyse multiple aspects semantic trajectories. MASTER conveys the idea that pure movement data can be enriched with multiple heterogeneous contextual aspects. These aspects are intimately interconnected and should be referenced as a whole as holistic trajectories. The scientific concept of MASTER is driven by five research challenges around the definition, management and analysis of holistic trajectories (see their website for further details).

RAMONES have liaised with MASTER during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project, agreeing to explore collaboration opportunities in the future.

- Liaised with the **H2020 VesselAI** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021
VesselAI aims at realising a holistic, beyond the state-of-the-art AI-empowered framework for decision-support models, data analytics and visualisations to build digital twins and maritime applications for a diverse set of cases with high impact, including simulating and predicting vessel behaviour and manoeuvring (including the human factor), ship energy design optimisation, autonomous shipping and fleet intelligence

RAMONES have liaised with the VesselAI (<https://vessel-ai.eu/>) during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had

direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project, agreeing to explore future grounds for collaborating..

- Liaised with the **H2020 Blue-Cloud** project with the first contact made on April 19th, 2021. Blue-Cloud (<https://blue-cloud.org/>), as the "Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative" of EU HORIZON 2020 programme, is the thematic EOSC for the marine domain, serving the Blue Economy, Marine Environment and Marine Knowledge agendas. Blue-Cloud delivers a collaborative virtual environment to enhance FAIR and Open Science. Started in October 2019, Blue-Cloud is deploying a cyber platform with smart federation of an unprecedented wealth of multidisciplinary data repositories, analytical tools, and computing facilities to explore and demonstrate the potential of cloud-based Open Science and address ocean sustainability, UN Ocean Decade, and G7 Future of the Oceans objectives. Blue-Cloud federates leading European marine Research infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, Euro-ARGO, ICOS, SOCAT, ENA, EMODnet, CMEMS) and e-Infrastructures (EUDAT, D4Science, WEKEO DIAS), allowing researchers to combine, reuse, and share quality data across disciplines and countries. The federation takes place at the levels of data, computing and analytical service resources.

RAMONES have liaised with the EU H2020 Blue-Cloud during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project, agreeing to strengthen their collaboration as the timeline of both projects progress.

- Liaised with the EU **WINTER** project with the first contact made on the 20th of September 2022.

The EU H2020 WINTER project (<https://winter-project.eu/>) is an Accompanying measure project funded from the RFCS 2021 Call with its main purpose of providing a Web INTERactive management tool for coal Regions in transition.

RAMONES have liaised with the WINTER and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project. An MoU between the two projects is being prepared and is expected to be signed soon.

3.3 Liaison with other projects and organizations

- Liaised with the VIRTUALDiver project and the first contact was made on April 19th, 2021. The Greece-funded VIRTUALDiver project (<https://www.virtualdiver.gr/>) aims at mass development and dissemination of "experiential" activities in coastal and submarine environments through the creation of a Comprehensive Digital Interaction Platform. The project output differentiates from the products created by competition, internationally, focusing on underwater environment and innovative technologies for single coastal capture and mainly in marine space, enhancing experiences through the geological interpretation of the volcanic engraved.

RAMONES have liaised with the VIRTUALDiver during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project.

- Liaised with the **i4SEA project** and the first contact was made on on April 19th, 2021

The i4SEA project (<https://www.i4sea.eu/en>) is a Greece-funded research project which aims at designing and developing an innovative platform for the collection and analysis of large marine surveillance data. The vision of the project is to efficiently and quickly process, integrate and analyze these data in order to create (a) a "Combined Real-time Business Image" and (b) a "Combined Historic Image" of Marine Surveillance. The project aspires to further develop already developed data processing techniques and to develop innovative software solutions utilizing cutting-edge research to be carried out within the project on in-memory databases, algorithms and parallel programming models and analytical methods data (big data analytics).

RAMONES have liaised with i4SEA during the Blue Research and Innovation Days Event (19-23 April 2021; <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>) and had direct exchange of information on the research objectives and prospects of each project.

- Liaised with the **NODDSUM** project and the first contact was made on on April 28th, 2021

The NODDSUM project is a French CNRS-funded proposal aiming at investigating the status of the marine environment in the depths of the Atlantic Ocean at a remote submarine site where legacy radioactive waste has been stored. The study will involve various parameters of surveying the location and the overall status of the site, including -among others- the monitoring of marine radioactivity at site. The project has been accepted for funding and is expected to start at the end of 2024.

RAMONES have liaised with the NODDSUM project after an invitation from the project officers. As the RAMONES technology is particularly fit for the objectives of NODDSUM, RAMONES have been invited to participate in the cruise. The collaboration between the projects will become stronger as both timelines progress.

- Liaised with the **SANTORY** project with the first contact made on the 20th of April 2021

The Greece-funded SANTORY project (<https://santory.gr/>) will establish a cutting-edge seafloor observatory using innovative marine technology (integrating hyperspectral and temperature sensors, a radiation spectrometer, fluid/gas samplers and pressure gauges) within the most-active submarine Mediterranean volcano, Kolumbo. It is located just 7 km NE (500m b.s.l.) of the well-known Santorini volcanic island and its hydrothermal system emits mantle-derived fluids consisting of nearly pure gaseous CO₂ together with aqueous fluids venting at 220°C. SANTORY will build an open-access data hub using innovative visualization and virtual reality technologies to present the volcanic dynamics driving scientific knowledge advances and communicating hazards to the society in easy to understand ways. The outcomes of SANTORY will provide the impetus for much needed multidisciplinary

collaboration in Greece and across the EU and will be a first step for understanding of such natural laboratories to underpin development of next-generation shallow volcanic seafloor observatories.

RAMONES and SANTORY share members of their consortia and the information channels remain continuously open. Each project develops independently, but complementarity in scientific data, methods and instrumentation provide the opportunities for strong synergy as the timelines of the progress evolve. A MoU has been signed between the projects.

- Liaised with the **Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society (HNPS)** with the first contact made on the 24 September 2021

The Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society (<http://hnps.eu>) is the major Society of researchers in Greece working in the field of Nuclear Physics and Applications with approximately 150 full members. The RAMONES PI (T.J. Mertzimekis) is the elected Secretary of the Society. The RAMONES team participated in the Annual Symposium of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society, which took place in the premises of NCSR “Demokritos” on 24 and 25 September 2021. The annual Symposium has an international character and features invited lectures from distinguished scientists from around the world. RAMONES have co-organized a dedicated session on Environmental Intelligence and Emerging Technologies supporting talks on next-generation research in nuclear energy and radiation applications. In parallel, a RAMONES booth was set up to distribute printed material to participants and disseminate our objectives and technological advances. The RAMONES project liaised with fellow scientists working in the field of nuclear and radiation physics, exploring potential collaboration in the near future, as well as with policy makers and stakeholders (members of the Greek Atomic Energy Agency Board, foreign representatives of international organizations etc).